

Contribution to the study of *Agrocybe pediades* complex (*Agaricales*) in Russia based on nrITS sequences

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Abstract. *Agrocybe pediades* is a rather widespread species mentioned in many Russian regional check-lists. However, there is no agreement among different authors concerning the volume of this species. Some of them recognize single polymorphic species *A. pediades* with several intraspecies groups. In this case *Agrocybe arenicola*, *A. semiorbicularis* and *A. subpediades* are accepted as synonyms of *A. pediades*. Under another above-listed species are considered as a group of close but separate taxa. In this research the representatives of *A. pediades* species complex collected in different parts of Russia have been studied using both molecular and morphological techniques. The analysis of nrITS1-5.8-ITS2 regions has revealed one large well supported clade consisting of specimens labeled before this study as *Agrocybe arenicola*, *A. pediades*, *A. semiorbicularis* and *A. subpediades*. This clade was characterized by the absence of the reliable morphological differences between included collections. The obtained results correspond to the wide species concept of *A. pediades*. Several small subclades have been also revealed inside the main clade. Most of them were inconstant with low bootstrap support in NJ, MP and ML analyses. They were shown to belong presumably to *A. pediades* var. *pediades*. One subclade recovered in all analyses with high bootstrap support was characterized by some distinct morphological features and was considered afterwards as a new variety of *A. pediades* – var. *bispora*. Therefore, all known so far Russian collections belong to *A. pediades* var. *pediades* and *A. pediades* var. *bispora*.

Key words: *Agrocybe pediades* complex, morphology, new variety, nrITS sequences, phylogenetic analysis, Russia

Introduction

Agrocybe pediades (Fr. : Fr.) Fayod is a rather widespread species reported from many regions of Russia. It is known to be saprotrophic inhabiting on nutrient-rich soils in usually human-disturbed localities, e.g. hayfields and pastures, grassy roadsides, gardens, dunes etc. Like some other members of the genus, *A. pediades* may be considered as a stress-tolerant species adapted to unfavourable environmental conditions (Watling 1989). This taxon has often been referred in many Russian regional check-lists due to its wide distribution. However, the taxonomic status of *A. pediades* has not sufficiently resolved until now. The problem of the

controversial interpretation is caused by its considerably variable morphological characters. At present there are two main morphological concepts concerning this taxon. Under one of them, *A. pediades* has been defined as a polymorphic species containing several intraspecies groups, which were considered by some authors as different varieties or forms (Nauta 2004, 2005). According to this point of view, *Agrocybe arenicola* (Berk.) Singer, *A. semiorbicularis* (Bull.) Fayod and *A. subpediades* (Murrill) Watling are recognized to be synonyms of *A. pediades*. Under another concept, there is a narrow taxonomic definition of *A. pediades* with the treatment of above-listed species as a group of close but independent taxa (Singer 1936; Watling 1982), which are

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distinguished generally by shape and colour of pileus, spore size and presence or absence of veil.

The application of mating test has allowed to discriminate three intersterile populations among American and European representatives of *A. pediades* s. lat. whereas isolates from Asia were either fully or partially interfertile with two of them (Rehner 1991). It has been hypothesized that “the genetic divergence associated with allopatry may be a significant factor in promoting speciation” in *A. pediades* complex. However, the author has not reported any concrete data on the geographical distribution of the revealed populations. The widely used approach of the relationships assay based on sequence analysis of the different genes have never been applied to this species complex up to date. There are a few data confirming only the belonging of *A. pediades* s. l. to the subgenus *Agrocybe* section *Pediadae* on the basis of the analysis of sequences and secondary structures of certain mSSU rRNA domains (Gonzales & Labarère 1998).

Nowadays, according to the narrow morphological concept, four species of *A. pediades* complex have been recorded in Russia. The purpose of the presented study is to examine the relationships between Russian collections based on both morphology and sequences of nrITS1-5.8S-ITS2 region to improve the understanding of species boundaries in *A. pediades* complex.

Materials and methods

Taxonomic sampling

The sampling included substantially Russian collections of *A. pediades* s. lat. (*A. pediades*, *A. arenicola*, *A. semiorbicularis* and *A. subpediades*). Besides Russian collections several specimens sampled in adjacent countries (mainly former USSR) were used also. The most of studied specimens was determined by different authors according to certain taxonomic interpretation. The original specimens' names written on their labels were checked and applied in the text. The most of the specimens used are kept in Mycological herbarium of Komarov Botanical Institute RAS (Saint Petersburg, LE) and herbarium of Institute of Biology and Soil RAS (Vladivostok, VLA-M). The pure cultures obtained from spore deposit of fresh fruit bodies are maintained in Basidiomycetes Culture Collection of Komarov Botanical Institute, RAS. The voucher specimens, geographical location and ecology, herbarium and/or culture collection numbers as well as GenBank accession numbers are listed in Table 1.

Morphological observations

We carried out morphological investigation of the specimens involved in molecular study to reveal discriminating characters for corresponding clades or subclades. The representatives of all subclades were analyzed totally, whereas the members of

the focal clade were examined randomly. The observations were focused generally on such characters of basidiome as the presence of veil, form of stipe, number of spores per basidium, spore dimensions and form of cheilocystidia. The collections were examined and drawn using standard microscopic techniques (Cléménçon 2009) with Micmed 2-2 (LOMO, St Petersburg, Russia) and AxioScop A1 (CarlZeiss, Goettingen, Germany) microscopes. For statistical evaluation of spore dimensions, 20–30 spores in both front and side views were measured per collection with the estimation of mean value of spore quotient Q^* (spore length / spore width in front and side projections) per studied group.

Molecular techniques

Total DNA was isolated mainly from herbarium specimens as well as pure cultures by scraping from medium surface. DNA extraction was carried out using CTAB extraction buffer with following steps of consecutive addition of Chloroform – Isoamyl alcohol mixture, Isopropyl alcohol – 3 M Sodium Acetate solution for precipitation, 70 % Ethanol for washing and finally EB buffer or water for dissolution. The alternative method of extraction DNA was using of DNA Easy Plant Mini Kit (Qiagen, Duesseldorf, Germany) according to manufacturer's instructions. The nrITS1-5.8S-ITS2 region was amplified with the fungal specific primers ITS1F and ITS4B (<http://www.biology.duke.edu/fungi/mycolab/primers.htm>). The PCR products were purified using QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit and PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen). Sequencing was performed with ABI model 3130 Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Carlsbad, USA) using BigDye™ Terminator Cycle Sequencing Ready Reaction Kit (Applied Biosystems) with the same primers. The raw data were processed using Sequencing Analysis 5.3.1 (Applied Biosystems). All sequences were deposited in GenBank with accession numbers given in Table 1.

Sequence alignment and phylogenetic analysis

All sequences were multiple aligned with MAFFT (<http://align.bmr.kyushu-u.ac.jp/mafft/online/server/>) with Q-INS-i strategy and default settings for other options. The analyses were subsequently performed using Neighbor-Joining (NJ), Maximum Likelihood (ML) and Maximum Parsimony (MP) methods in MEGA 5 (Tamura *et al.* 2011), the RAXML servers (<http://phylobench.vital-it.ch/raxml-bb/index.php>, which implements the search protocol of Stamatakis *et al.* 2008) and in PAUP* 4b10 (Swofford 2002) respectively. Analyses were carried out with following parameters: 1) NJ: Tamura 3-parameter model, with 1000 bootstrap (BS) replications; 2) ML: GTR model with 100 rapid BS replications; 3) MP: heuristic searches algorithm with tree bisection-reconnection (TBR) branch swapping, 100 replications of random stepwise sequence addition; one tree was held at each step

Table 1. Collections used in this study, their geographical origin, ecology, herbarium and/or culture number, GenBank accession number

Taxon*	Geographic origin, date of collection	Ecology	Herbarium / Culture No	GenBank accession No
<i>A. pediades</i> var. <i>pediades</i>	Russia, EP, Leningrad Region, 3 Aug 2004	hayfield	LE 262815 / Cult. 2177	JN684788
<i>A. pediades</i> var. <i>pediades</i>	Russia, EP, Leningrad Region, 3 Aug 2004	hayfield	LE 212081 / Cult. 2169	JN684772
<i>A. pediades</i> var. <i>pediades</i>	Russia, EP, Leningrad Region, 4 Aug 2010	on sand at the margin of road	LE 262812 / Cult. 2168	JN684775
<i>A. pediades</i> var. <i>pediades</i>	Russia, EP, Ryazan Region, 13 Aug 2006	grassland	LE 246093	JN684792
<i>A. pediades</i> var. <i>pediades</i>	Russia, EP, Bryansk Region, 25 Jul 2007	grassland	LE 254453 / Cult. 2218	JN684777
<i>A. pediades</i> var. <i>pediades</i>	Russia, EP, Bryansk Region, 25 Jul 2007	grassland at aspen-birch grove	LE 254454 / Cult. 2219	JN684778
<i>A. pediades</i> var. <i>pediades</i>	Russia, EP, Samara Region, 3 Jul 2005	grassland	LE 234397	JN684793
<i>A. pediades</i> f. <i>bispora</i>	Russia, AP, Irkutsk Region, 17 Aug 1981	on a path at the edge of the forest	LE 11398 (type)	JN684774
<i>A. pediades</i> f. <i>bispora</i>	Mongolia, East-Central Asia, 20 Aug 1985	on sandy soil, steppe	LE 202270	JN684791
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, EP, Leningrad Region, 3 Aug 2004	hayfield	LE 262814 / Cult. 2170	JN684776
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, Western Caucasus, 23 Jul 1995	grassland	LE 262822	JN684780
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, Western Caucasus, 5 Jul 1999	grassland	LE 262823	JN684779
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, AP, Altaysky Territory, 12 Aug 2003	steppe	LE 262813	JN684787
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, AP, Novosibirsk Region, 30 Jun 2005	mat-grass steppe	LE 262833	JN684786
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, AP, Novosibirsk Region, 7 Jun 2007	lawn	LE 262824	JN684785
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, AP, Primorsky Territory, 16 Aug 1994	grazing	VLA M-5566	JN684789
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, AP, Primorsky Territory, 8 Jun 2001	field	VLA M-15488	JN684781
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, AP, Primorsky Territory, 8 Jul 2009	on sawdust	LE 262825	JN684782
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, AP, Primorsky Territory, 9 Jul 2009	field	LE 262831	JN684783
<i>A. pediades</i>	Russia, AP, Primorsky Territory, 16 Jul 2009	field	LE 262832	JN684784
<i>A. semiorbicularis</i>	Rep. Latvia, vic. Riga, 18 Jul 1988	NA	LE 18096	JN684803
<i>A. semiorbicularis</i>	Russia, EP, Leningrad Region, 3 Aug 2004	hayfield	LE 262821	JN684799
<i>A. semiorbicularis</i>	Russia, EP, Pskov Region, 6 Jul 1994	glade in the forest	LE 208106	JN684802
<i>A. semiorbicularis</i>	Rep. Azerbaijan, South Caucasus, 13 Oct 1966	grassland	LE 11484	JN684800
<i>A. semiorbicularis</i>	Russia, AP, Altaysky Territory, 20 Sep 2003	steppe	LE 262811	JN684798
<i>A. semiorbicularis</i>	Russia, AP, Krasnoyarsk Region, 2 Aug 1964	on a path at the forest edge	LE 11478	JN684801
<i>A. semiorbicularis</i>	Russia, AP, Novosibirsk Region 29 Jun 2007	grassland in dendrarium	LE 269118	JN684797
<i>A. subpediades</i>	Russia, EP, Novgorod Region, 4 Aug 2001	on a path at the forest edge	LE 217897	JN684796
<i>A. subpediades</i>	Russia, EP, Novgorod Region, 4 Aug 2001	sandpit	LE 217898	JN684795
<i>A. subpediades</i>	Russia, EP, Tula Region, 22 Jun 2003	field	LE 234899	JN684790
<i>A. arenicola</i>	Kyrgyz Rep., Central Asia, 12 Jul 1970	steppe	LE 11357	JN684805
<i>A. arenicola</i>	Rep. Kazakhstan, Central Asia, 3 Jun 1978	plantations of trees	LE 11358	JN684804
<i>Agrocybe</i> sp.	Turkmenistan, Central Asia, Mar 1948	on sandy soil in association with <i>Haloxylon aphyllum</i> , <i>H. persicum</i> , <i>Salsola richteri</i> , <i>Calligonum</i> sp.	LE 11405	JN684794
<i>Agrocybe</i> cf. <i>ochracea</i>	Mongolia, East-Central Asia, 20 Aug 1985	on sandy soil at the border of birch forest	LE 202260	JN684773

* taxon names as identified before this study

Abbreviations: EP – European part of Russia; AP – Asian part of Russia

Fig. 1. Phylogenetic tree of *Agrocybe pediades* and related taxa based on sequences of the nrITS1-5.8S-ITS2 region. The rooted tree was constructed with the Neighbor-Joining analysis. Bootstrap values (%) are shown above the branches. The grey rectangles indicate the subclades with corresponding numbers.

during stepwise addition and the number of trees retained was limited to 100. Gaps were treated as missing data and given equal weight. The groups with a support of $\geq 55\%$ were retained in all analyses.

For all analyses the sequences of *Alnicola umbrina* (Maire) Kühner and *A. badia* Kühner retrieved from GenBank were chosen as outgroup based on BLAST homology and recent data (Moreau *et al.* 2006).

Altogether 38 nrDNA ITS sequences were used for phylogenetic analysis of the *A. pediades* species complex, from which 36 sequences were generated during this study from collections originally named *A. arenicola* (Berk.) Singer, *A. pediades*, *A. pediades* f. *bispora* A.N. Petrov, *A. semiorbicularis* and *A. subpediades*.

All the analyses revealed some subclades. The largest one is a subclade I formed by five collections labeled as *A. pediades* and *A. subpediades* from European and Asian parts of Russia. It received moderate to high statistical support in NJ and ML analyses (65 % and 100 % respectively), but was not recovered in MP fifty percent majority rule consensus tree. Both NJ and ML analyses showed the presence of other small subclades (II, III, IV) inside the main clade, but the constancy of these subclades was uncertain due to their absence in MP resulted tree and varying statistical support.

The collection LE 11405 labeled by collectors as *A. pediades* is placed as the basal taxon to the main clade in all phylogenies with high BS value (Figs 1–2) and is characterized by the most degree of the phylogenetic distance (0.042) with the main clade. The collection LE 202260 originally labeled as *A. pediades* f. *bispora* is a sister to the rest of the taxa, having a little phylogenetic distance (0.011) with them.

Observations on morphology, ecology and geographical distribution of revealed groups

The morphological examination showed a little variation of macro- and micromorphological features between collections studied. The obtained morphological data are summarized in Table 2. The general description of each recognized clade and subclade are followed:

1) Focal clade embraces the majority of collections studied. There are specimens identified initially as *A. arenicola*, *A. pediades*, *A. semiorbicularis* and *A. subpediades* and collected throughout Russia from European part to Russian Far East as well as some Central Asian countries in this clade. Its representatives were recorded from open, usually sandy habitats, margins of roads, hayfields, fields, grasslands and from undisturbed steppe also. In spite of almost identical ITS sequences, morphological features of mentioned specimens can slightly vary. Veil is usually absent, but some collections have its traces at the margin of pileus. The stipe bases are not inflated. Cheilocystidia are from lageniform and bottle-shaped (sometimes subcapitate to distinctly capitate) to lecythiform, while the capitate and not capitate types may be presented in one mount; some cheilocystidia have unusual forked necks (Figs. 3a–b). Pleurocystidia are not observed. Spores are broadly ellipsoid to ovoid, not or only slightly mitriform in frontal view and broadly ellipsoid to oblong or amygdaliform in side view with large central or slightly eccentric pore up to 2.0 μm in diameter, slightly flattened, with spore quotient $Q_{\text{front}}^* = 1.49$, $Q_{\text{side}}^* = 1.61$. Basidia are 2- and 4-spored, usually with the prevalence of 4-spored type.

2) Subclade I includes five collections. The members of this subclade are diverse in ecological characteristics, but tend towards growing in forested places. Geographically, the representatives of this group are widely distributed in European part of Russia and Siberia, while they ITS sequences are identical. All collections are characterized by stipe with distinct basal bulb often with mycelial strands. Veil remnants

are absent absolutely. Cheilocystidia are lageniform, tend more towards having a distinct apical head (Figs 3e–f). Spores are broadly ellipsoid (with large proportion of amygdaliform or mitriform) having central large pore (up to 2.7 μm), with spore quotient $Q_{\text{front}}^* = 1.53$, $Q_{\text{side}}^* = 1.69$. There is a large proportion of 2-spored basidia together with 4-spored ones in the hymenium.

3) Subclade II is represented by two collections. They were found in European part of Russia and Siberia growing in open places (grasslands or steppe). The studied specimens are characterized by cylindrical stipe without any bulb at base and by absence of veil. They also have somewhat atypical lageniform cheilocystidia with narrow to sharp apex. Spores (originated from only 4-spored basidia) are broadly ellipsoid or slightly amygdaliform, but never mitriform, with distinct eccentric pore (up to 2 μm) and $Q_{\text{front}}^* = 1.5$, $Q_{\text{side}}^* = 1.65$.

4) Subclade III consists of two collections both from Asian part of Russia growing in open places (mat-grass steppe and field). Its representatives are characterized by stipes not inflated at the base and missing or poorly marked veil remnants. Cheilocystidia are from irregularly lageniform to bottle-shaped or lecythiform, sometimes with unusual forked necks; distinct apical heads are presented in most cases along with not capitate types (Figs 3c–d). Spores are broadly ellipsoid to ovoid, some with tend towards mitriform shape in frontal view, broadly ellipsoid in side view, slightly flattened ($Q_{\text{front}}^* = 1.47$, $Q_{\text{side}}^* = 1.59$), with large, sometimes eccentric pore up to 2.2 μm . One collection (LE 262833) has very large (up to 21.7 \times 14.5 μm), misshapen, truncate to near triangular spores, originated probably from 1-spored basidia. This collection is characterized by having 2- and 1-spored basidia (2-spored is predominated), whereas collection from Far East (VLA M-15488) possess 2- and 4-spored ones with the prevalence of 4-spored type.

5) Subclade IV includes two collections from Europe (vic. Riga, Latvia) and East-Central Asia (northern Mongolia). They both are characterized by slightly tapering stipes, absent of velar remnants, more or less lageniform to bottle-shaped or lecythiform cheilocystidia mostly with distinct apical heads. Spores are broadly ellipsoid in both views, not or very little flattened ($Q_{\text{front}}^* = 1.57$, $Q_{\text{side}}^* = 1.63$), with large central pore up to 2.0 μm . Basidia are 2- and 4-spored.

The collection LE 202260 from East-Central Asia (northern Mongolia) was found in a steppe at a birch forest margin, on sandy soil. Its specimens have slightly broadened base of stipes, no traces of velum, fusiform or ampulliform cheilocystidia without distinct heads and broadly ellipsoid to oblong, slightly flattened spores ($Q_{\text{front}}^* = 1.69$, $Q_{\text{side}}^* = 1.78$) with large, somewhat eccentric pore (up to 2.2 μm). Basidia are 2- and 4-spored in more or less equal portions. The main distinguished feature of this collection is the presence of conspicuous fusiform pleurocystidia. They are similar to cheilocystidia in shape but are considerably larger (65.0–66.0 \times 16.0–17.0 \times 3.9–5.5 μm).

Agrocybe sp. (LE 11405) is represented by one collection from Central Asia (Turkmenistan, East Karakum Desert,

Repetek station). It was identified initially as *A. pediades* but our study revealed the significant differences from above-mentioned species regarding both morphological (spore dimensions, very small to lacking pore) and molecular features. It may be suggested that this collection belongs rather to the subgenus *Aporus* Singer. The taxonomic status of this collection needs further investigation.

Thus, the analysis of main distinguished morphological features shows their significant overlapping between collections studied. There are only weak differences between revealed clade and subclades. Subclade I, including collections of *A. pediades* f. *bispora* (typus), *A. pediades* and *A. subpediades*, differs from others by having basal bulb and the most flattened spores, often mitriform-shaped. Subclade II with specimens labeled *A. pediades* and *A. semiorbicularis* possess lageniform cheilocystidia with sharp apex and 4-spored basidia only. Subclade III and IV (*A. pediades*, *A. pediades* f. *bispora*, *A. semiorbicularis*) are rather similar to the focal clade. First of them differs from the main clade only in the presence of 1-spored, absence of 4-spored basidia and some proportion of very large misshapen spores. Subclade IV is characterized by the least flattened spores among all groups. Subclades II, III and IV are not recovered in all analyses and have varying statistical support. The collection LE 202260 representing the sister branch to the main clade on all trees is clearly distinguished from others by shape of cheilocystidia, presence of large pleurocystidia and usually not flattened spores, although spore dimensions are overlapping (Figs 3g–i). The presence of pleurocystidia makes this collection similar to *A. ochracea* Nauta, but it differs from the latter by their shape and spore size. Therefore, it may be best considered this taxon currently as *Agrocybe* cf. *ochracea*.

Discussion

The phylogenetic analysis showed rather weak discrimination between the representatives of *A. pediades* species complex. The collections belonging to the *A. pediades*, *A. subpediades* and to the *A. semiorbicularis* in R. Watling's sense (1982) as well as R. Singer's *A. arenicola* (1936) were grouped together within one highly supported but unresolved clade with almost identical ITS sequences. Our morphological and ecological observations revealed the wide range of the variability and the absence of clear distinguishing features between specimens from Russian collections fallen in the focal clade. This result may indicate the species *A. pediades* is a single taxon. The obtained data corresponds to the wide definition of M. Nauta (2005), who has treated *A. arenicola*, *A. semiorbicularis* and *A. subpediades* as synonyms to *A. pediades*. Thereby it should be considered, that the specimens referred in many regional Russian check-lists as *A. arenicola*, *A. semiorbicularis* and *A. subpediades* belong actually to *A. pediades*.

The genetic similarity of geographically distant collections (e.g. from Leningrad Region and Russian Far East or Central Asia) can be explained by two reasons. On the one hand, the

new data on resolving potential of nrITS sequences in some fungal groups has recently been accumulated. It has been found that nrITS sequences appear to be either too variable or, on the contrary, too conserved for being applied on species level (Peintner 2007). The last situation was discovered, for example, in the genus *Alnicola* (Moreau *et al.* 2006) chosen here as outgroup. Thus, it may be assumed that using of nrITS sequences only is insufficient for more accurate discrimination of the phylogenetic groups within *A. pediades* s. lat. On the other hand, the absence of clear influence of geographical signal to the degree of the genetic divergence between studied collections may be connected with mostly anthropochorous pattern of the populations distribution.

The small non-constant subclades II, III and IV with varying BS and vague morphological differences should belong to *A. pediades* also. The presence of them suggests to suppose that some microevolutionary processes have been occurred inside the transcontinental distributed species *A. pediades*. However the correlation between revealed subclades and their geographical distribution and / or ecological requirements was not found.

M. Nauta (2004) has proposed two varieties under species *A. pediades* besides type variety: *fimicola* (Speg.) Nauta and *cinctula* Nauta. They have been described based on both morphological and ecological characters: the presence of annulus for var. *cinctula*; distinct veil remnants at pileus margin and inhabiting on dung for var. *fimicola*. These varieties were not represented in our sampling and were not registered in Russia up to now. Therefore, the Russian specimens fallen into the main clade and subclades II, III and IV should be considered as *A. pediades* var. *pediades*.

The separation subclade I composed of five collections, including type specimen of f. *bispora*, was moderate to highly supported in all the analyses (Figs 1–2). A. Petrov (1983) has recognized the presence solely 2-spored basidia and connected with this larger spore size as principal distinguished characters for his new forma. Our observations showed that 2-spored basidia are presented in almost each collection (except subclade II). The collections having a considerable proportion of 2-spored basidia are characterized also by great range of spore size variability. In addition the type specimens (LE 11398) were found to have some proportion of 1-spored basidia in the hymenium while the other representatives of this subclade possessed some percentage of 4-spored ones. Therefore the number of spores per basidium cannot be considered as a main delimiting character. In our study collections included in subclade I have been characterized by the presence of basal bulb on stipe and shape of spores also. According to the set of these characters (Table 2, Figs 3e–f), it seems likely that the f. *bispora* described by Petrov (1983) is in fact a natural unit, though it needs to expand the taxonomic interpretation. It is noteworthy, that the basal bulb on stipe has been considered by R. Watling (1989) as an essential feature of *A. subpediades*. Thus, subclade I combines the characters of *A. subpediades* with *A. pediades* f. *bispora* and is considered as variety here with the proposal of a new combination var. *bispora*.

Fig. 3. *Agrocybe pediades* var. *pediades* main clade: a – cheilocystidia, b – spores; *A. pediades* var. *pediades* subclade III: c - cheilocystidia, d - spores; *A. pediades* var. *bispora* subclade I: e - cheilocystidia, f - spores; *A. cf. ochracea* sister group: g - cheilocystidia, h – pleurocystidia, i – spores. Scale bar = 10 μ m

Table 2. Morphological characters of the revealed phylogenetic groups

Character	Focal clade	Subclade I	Subclade II	Subclade III	Subclade IV	Subclade V
Ecology	fields, grasslands, hayfields, often on sandy soils, roadsides	predominantly in forested places	grasslands or steppe	steppe or field	steppe, sandy soils	steppe at a birch forest margin, on sandy soil
Stipe	even cylindrical	with distinct basal bulb, often with mycelial strands	even cylindrical	even cylindrical	slightly tapering at the base	broadened at the base
Veil	without any remnants	without any remnants	without any remnants	without or with traces at the cap margin	without any remnants	without any remnants
Cheilocystidia	irregularly lageniform, bottle-shaped to lecythiform, mostly subcapitate to capitate, sometimes forked	lageniform with round apical head	lageniform with narrow to sharp apex	irregularly lageniform to bottle-shaped or lecythiform, mostly with apical head, sometimes forked	irregularly lageniform to bottle-shaped or lecythiform, mostly with apical head	fusiform to ampulliform without distinct head
Spores	in frontal view broadly ellipsoid to ovoid, not or slightly mitriform	broadly ellipsoid with large proportion of amygdaliform or mitriform	broadly ellipsoid or slightly amygdaliform	in frontal view broadly ellipsoid to ovoid, some with tend to mitriform	in frontal view broadly ellipsoid with tend to mitriform	broadly ellipsoid in both views
Spores	in side view broadly ellipsoid to oblong or amygdaloid, 10.9–16.7 × 7.7–10.8 × 7.4–10.3 μm Q _F * = 1.49, Q _S * = 1.60	(12) 13–19 (20.3) × 8–13 × 7.6–12.2 (13.5) μm; Q _F * = 1.53, Q _S * = 1.69	(12.7) 13.2–14.3 (15) × 8–9.5 (10.8) × 7.8–8.6 (9.2) μm; Q _F * = 1.50, Q _S * = 1.65	in side view broadly ellipsoid, 11.1–18.8 (21.7) × 7.5–11.6 × 7.3–11.3 (14.5) μm Q _F * = 1.47, Q _S * = 1.59	in side view broadly ellipsoid, 11.8–15.6 (20.1) × 7.4–12.6 × 7.2–13.1 μm Q _F * = 1.57, Q _S * = 1.63	13.9–18.8 × 9.0–11.5 × 8.7–11.2 μm Q _F * = 1.67, Q _S * = 1.68
Spore number per basidia	2 and 4	2 and 4	4	1, 2 and 4	2 and 4	2 and 4
Pleurocystidia	-	-	-	-	-	not capitate, fusiform, like cheilocystidia but larger

Q_F* - mean value of spore quotient (spore length / spore width) in frontal view; Q_S* - mean value of spore quotient in side view

Agrocybe pediades var. *bispora* (A.N. Petrov) E.F. Malysheva & Kiyashko, *comb. nov.*

Basionym: *Agrocybe pediades* f. *bispora* A.N. Petrov, Mikol. Fitopatol. 17(1): 43 (1983).

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It differs from the type variety in the presence of bulb at stipe base, large spores with tend to mitriform shape and high percentage of 1–2-spored basidia.

Habitat and distribution: solitary or in small groups on soil in grasslands and roadsides, usually in human disturbed places; known from European part of Russia and Siberia.

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